

PaNOSC

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Table of Content

Project Deliverable Information Sheet	2
Document Control Sheet	2
List of participants	2
Table of Content	3
1 Introduction	4
2 Use case: Transparent data transfer for Analysis Services.....	5
2.1 Story.....	5
2.2 Actors	6
2.3 Additional constraints	6
3 Technical components	6
3.1 Data transfer solution.....	6
3.2 PaNOSC RI typical archive	7
3.3 Analysis Service.....	8
3.4 AAI	8
4 The pilot.....	8
4.1 Oneprovider service	9
4.2 AAI Setup	10
4.3 Jupyter notebook set up.....	12
5 Performance results	13
6 Conclusion	14
7 Annex: implementation notes.....	15
7.1 About this document.....	16
7.2 Background information.....	16
7.3 PART I - Install and configure the OneZone service	19
7.4 PART II - Install and configure the Oneprovider services	28
7.5 PART III - Create a K8s cluster with EC3	36
7.6 PART IV - Configure the K8s cluster to spawn Jupyter notebooks	42
7.7 PART V - Configure a Binder instance to spawn Jupyter notebooks.....	50

1. Introduction

Until recently, most Neutron and X-ray (Photon and Neutron also known as PaN) facility users had to use predominantly portable media to transfer data produced by the research infrastructure's (RI) instruments to their home lab for analyses. This was the predominant model some years ago, when the volume of data was relatively low and compatible with the network, the storage and the compute capacity of the facility users' organisations.

Today with the huge boost of the volume of experimental data (dozens of PB per year), the complexity of data treatment, the need for FAIR¹ science, does this historical model still fit the need? Does the data need to be transferred by the scientists to their home organisation for analysis with their own organisation's resources?

The notion of users has also evolved; Nine years ago (ILL and UKRI ISIS were the first RIs in the community to publish their data policy based on the open data principles in 2011) the term users was only referring to the scientists that have submitted a scientific proposal to access the RIs' instruments, today since the publication of RI Open Data Policy, this term also encompasses the data scientists that are taking advantage of the RI open data without visiting the RI premises.

Consequently, there is a major shift from local to remote access and treatment of data that needs to be handled. What are the alternative models? How do these data and associated services integrate with the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)?

In 2020, the volume of the raw data produced for a single experiment in a photon or neutron RI ranges from some hundreds of MB to 100 TB depending on the instrument technique. This 10⁶-scale factor, associated with the large spectrum of scientific communities with very diverse practices (from large nuclear physics groups to individual scientists, covering a large number of scientific domains including industrial research) makes it extremely difficult to propose a single model for the scientists that want to process data.

These are some of the questions that PaNOSC, and especially WP6 with the support of ExPANDS and GÉANT, are trying to answer for the Photon and Neutron community. In this WP, we explore the technical infrastructure solutions available and the organisation that would allow fitting these requirements.

¹ Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable

2 Use case: Transparent data transfer for Analysis Services

The work of WP6 concerning data transfer is driven by 3 different uses cases where we try to explore the technical solutions available today, to understand their limits and how they could be integrated in the RIs ecosystem (technical integration, sustainability, investment and operational cost, support organisation, ...):

1. A RI wants to archive its experimental data in a remote data centre.
2. A user wants to access a data analysis service, data has to be available “transparently”.
3. A facility user wants to transfer a large dataset from an RI’s archive to a remote compute centre or her or his home pc.

In the work related to this deliverable, we are exploring the 2nd use case where a scientist wants to access a data analysis service offered by another organisation. The compute resources, where the service lives, are distant from the RI archive holding the data.

The generic term “archive” could cover different situations and levels of service: from the “cold archive” ensuring the bit-level preservation of the files to the platform that allows users to combine data of different provenance, including the “repository” that encompasses user access and richer metadata description. If use case 1 is clearly referring to the “cold archive”, use case 2 presented in this report is more in line with the “platform” definition.

2.1 Story

A scientist wants to access an online **EOSC service** to perform analysis **on a data set archived by one of the PaNOSC RIs**.

The computing and data infrastructures are distant.

The service could be operated by a different organisation than the RI.

The scientist should be able to **access data** from the RIs and store back the results at the same archive facility in **a transparent manner**, i.e. the scientist does not have to carry the data back and forth.

Due to the variety of analysis software² that could be used and in order to provide a standard performance experience (we want to avoid users having greatly different experiences depending on the software used and the geographical location of the compute resources), it appears to be necessary that the analysis service could benefit from a local cache of the data.

Datasets could be open data, therefore accessible by anyone already registered at the facility.

Datasets could still be under embargo. In this case data could only be accessed by a user with **sufficient authorisations** i.e. the user has to be part of the proposal/experimental team or is already authorised by this team to access the data. The process to grant additional access rights is not part of this use case.

Users’ authentication is performed through the **PaN community AAI³ UmbrellaID⁴**.

² <https://software.pan-data.eu>

³ AAI: Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure

⁴ <https://umbrellaid.org>

Data access authorisation is performed at the facility level. This is the current scheme in the PaN community where users have a local account at each facility and an UmbrellaID account. The authorisations are associated with this local account. A bridge mechanism has to associate the local and community account id to perform authorisation when the users want to access the services or data with their community account.

The RIs offer a service to host the results of the analyses, but the users could decide to host them elsewhere under their own responsibility.

2.2 Actors

The user could be a **data scientist** that has never performed any experiment at the RI, he or she wants to access open data.

The user could also be a **facility user** that wants to analyse data that are still under embargo following an experiment she or he has recently performed at the RI.

The **organisation** (EGI in our pilot) **providing the data analysis service.**

The **RI holding the data archive** (CERIC-ERIC in our initial pilot).

2.3 Additional constraints

This use case could be further extended to a scenario where the service platform and the data archive could be part of different AAI. Both implementing the AARC blueprint architecture⁵, this case should as well be transparent for the users i.e. users should have to authenticate only once.

3 Technical components

3.1 Data transfer solution

To better understand the potential technical choices and to discuss the needs with the solution providers, a technical workshop⁶ was jointly organised by the EGI community with the ESCAPE⁷ and XDC⁸ H2020 projects in Amsterdam in July 2019. During this workshop the PaNOSC data transfer use cases were presented and discussed.

The necessity to have a local cache of the data at the analysis service location and the authorisation mechanism of the community that necessitates a translation of the User ID between the community and the RI local accounts drove us to first test the EGI DataHub service⁹, which is based on the Onedata¹⁰ software stack.

The main components¹¹ of Onedata are:

- Spaces, which are distributed data volumes, that users can access and organise,
- Zone, which is the federation of providers. The Onezone service has been installed by EGI and is the core of the EGI DataHub. A specific zone has been created for PaNOSC,
- Providers are the entities that support Spaces and provide the data storage.

5 <https://aarc-project.eu/architecture/>

6 Workshop on data management <https://indico.egi.eu/event/4698/>

7 <https://projectescape.eu/>

8 <http://www.extreme-datacloud.eu/>

9 <https://www.egi.eu/about/newsletters/introducing-the-egi-datahub-prototype/>

10 <https://onedata.org>

11 https://onedata.org/#/home/documentation/doc/getting_started/what_is_onedata.html

3.2 PaNOSC RI typical archive

The historical and still main role of the storage archive at a PaN facility is storing data produced by the detectors of the scientific instruments. As data is the main output of the RI, this is a highly critical role when the instruments are running that quite often necessitate a protected network bandwidth to ensure the minimal performance required by the experiment.

A typical architecture is presented in Figure 1. The central archive collects the data directly from the instruments, but also serves the access for user transfers and analysis through gateways to control that these accesses do not disturb the acquisition processes. The gateways also offer standard access protocol like NFS¹², SMB¹³, FTP¹⁴, rsync¹⁵ ... The users can access the services directly exposed by the gateways using their own RI credentials, these are the local IDs that are used by the authorisations mechanisms (ACLs¹⁶).

Figure 1 Typical PaN RI archive architecture

Hereafter is presented a typical file size distribution for a neutron facility. It ranges from dozens of KB to 4GB, with most of the files around 1 GB.

¹² NFS: Network File System
¹³ SMB: Server Message Block
¹⁴ FTP: File Transfer Protocol
¹⁵ rsync: remote synchronization
¹⁶ ACL: Access Control List

Figure 2 typical file size distribution for a neutron archive (ILL)

3.3 Analysis Service

PaNOSC's WP4 is developing two data analysis services, one based on the use of remote desktop and the second based on Jupyter notebooks¹⁷. Regarding this pilot, as EGI was already offering their EGI Notebooks service¹⁸ based on JupyterHub technology (Jupyterhub is a virtual environment where users can combine documentation with code and dataset and share the resulting notebook with the community) at TRL8¹⁹, we opted for this service to evaluate the integration with the data transfer solution.

3.4 AAI

UmbrellaID, the PaN community AAI, is obviously part of the pilot. Since the beginning of the PaNOSC project in the scope of Task 6.4, UmbrellaID has integrated the GÉANT eduTEAMS²⁰ platform and consequently became compliant with the AARC blueprint architecture. The standard EGI Notebook service is accessible through the EGI Check-in²¹ which is also compliant with the AARC blueprint architecture.

4 The pilot

The pilot was performed using the CERIC-ERIC archive, located in Trieste, acting as the data provider. The analysis service was provided by the EGI cloud and the EGI Notebooks services

¹⁷ <https://jupyter.org>

¹⁸ <https://www.egi.eu/services/notebooks/>

¹⁹ https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/wp/2014_2015/annexes/h2020-wp1415-annex-g-trl_en.pdf

²⁰ <https://eduteams.org/>

²¹ <https://www.egi.eu/services/check-in>

hosted by CESNET²² (Czech Republic). The EGI Notebooks service was tailored to support UmbrellaID, the PaN community AAI.

The Onezone service was set up and operated by EGI.

The Oneprovider service was set up by CERIC-ERIC.

The comprehensive description of the installation and the documentation for deploying this setup to other organisations is provided in Annexe I. We will focus in this section the findings that are more specific to the PaN RI community.

4.1 Oneprovider service

RIs have to set-up the Oneprovider services (Docker, VM or physical server) with LUMA²³ instances in their LAN²⁴ if they do not want to expose directly their protocol gateways (NFS gateway for instance). LUMA is a Onedata service that allows custom mapping between local user accounts or credential on storage resources (e.g. POSIX user ID/group ID, LDAP DN, Ceph username, GlusterFS UID/GID, etc.) to Onedata user accounts.

By design, the Oneprovider service requires complete control (root) on the storage disk in order to write the data on behalf of the users (need to properly set ownership on the storage). Considering the importance and sensitivity of these archives for the RI production, we do not want to connect directly the Oneprovider services to the RI archives.

To avoid Onedata changing file permissions on the production storage (Central Archive in Fig. 1) when the user registers back the outcome of the analysis, the following workaround has been considered and implemented.

Figure 3 Oneprovider interaction with RI archive

A dedicated Oneprovider instance has been set up at CERIC-ERIC for reading the data from the NFS gateways and a second one was set up only for the purpose of writing back the data to an

²² <https://www.cesnet.cz/?lang=en>

²³ https://onedata.org/docs/doc/administering_onedata/luma.html

²⁴ LAN: Local Area Network

isolated storage on the LAN of the RI. During the data transfer pilot, a Jupyter notebook was also prepared to read hdf5 datasets made available by the PaNOSC facility through the EGI DataHub volume space, analyse datasets using the h5glance²⁵ library developed by the European XFEL²⁶, and produce as result a plot. To access datasets from the Onedata volume space the OnedataFS²⁷ library was also used. The resulting plot, generated in the user's space of the Jupyter notebook, was also sent back to the facility through the oneprovider service instance enabled for write access. A simple synchronisation mechanism was then set up (rsync) to copy back the data from this storage to the central archive. The synchronisation is triggered using the inotify api monitoring filesystem events. This is not an ideal solution as it introduces delays in the process, but this is perfectly acceptable for our use case. In this scenario, the datasets are read from the volume space and used with Jupyter to perform some computations. The outputs of the computation will be stored in another volume space.

4.2 AAI Setup

Fig. 4 presents the initial setup where PaNOSC users, using the Umbrella AAI provided by GÉANT eduTEAMS, should be able to access the EGI Notebook service, which is federated through the EGI Check-in Infrastructure SP Proxy using OpenID Connect. In this setup, the EGI Check-in Infrastructure SP Proxy is connected to the Umbrella AAI as a SAML²⁸ Service Provider.

From the point of view of a PaNOSC user, the expectation is that the user will be able to:

1. Register once at the UmbrellaID AAI.
2. Login to the EGI Notebook Service using their UmbrellaID through the Umbrella AAI without having to register again.
3. Use the EGI Notebook Service to submit computation flows.
4. The computation flows will run on the EGI Compute Infrastructure.
5. The computation flows will be able to access (read input and write output data) to the data archive at the RI where the user data are archived.

²⁵ <https://github.com/European-XFEL/h5glance>

²⁶ <https://www.xfel.eu/>

²⁷ <https://github.com/onedata/fs-onedatafs>

²⁸ SAML: Security Assertion Markup Language

Figure 4 Compute service and data access from different community (different AAI proxy)

In order to achieve the above, the following has to happen:

- Technical connection of EGI Check-In as a SAML Service Provider to the Umbrella AAI.
- Attribute release from Umbrella AAI to EGI Check-In with all the required attributes, so that the user does not have to enter personal information manually on the EGI Check-In.
- Alignment of the Acceptable Usage Policies (AUP) of UmbrellaID AAI and EGI Check-In with the WISE²⁹ Baseline³⁰ so that the user can accept the Umbrella AAI AUP once they register (and not having to accept again the EGI AUP).
- Configuration of EGI Check-In to map Umbrella AAI entitlements to the access rights used internally in EGI.
- Enable the computational flows running on the EGI Compute Infrastructure to access data in the Data Archive service of the PaNOSC RIs.

During this period WP6 team members have started the integration work, with the following actions still pending:

- Regarding the attribute release from Umbrella AAI to EGI Check-In, we need to proceed to the next phase of the migration from UmbrellaID to the Umbrella AAI service, where users will be able to register on the UmbrellaID AAI and provide verified e-mail addresses
- Regarding the Acceptable Usage Policies, further work is required in aligning with the WISE baseline
- The configuration of EGI Check-In to properly map Umbrella Entitlements will happen after the attribute release is implemented
- Regarding the enablement of the computational flows running on the EGI Compute Infrastructure to access data in the Data Archive service of the PaNOSC RIs, this is not technically possible at the moment. It is a known problem of the AARC Blueprint Architecture and the AARC Community and EOSC AAI Task Force are working on a prototype solution that should be available later this year.

Taking into account the above, for building this pilot we have simplified the set-up: the EGI Notebook instance was configured as a Service Provider of UmbrellaID as illustrated in Fig 4. All

²⁹ <https://wise-community.org>

³⁰ <https://wiki.geant.org/display/WISE/Baseline+Acceptable+Use+Policy+and+Conditions+of+Use>

the components perform authentication through the UmbrellaID infrastructure.

Figure 5 Compute service and data access in the same community (same AAI)

4.3 Jupyter notebook set up

In order to access and save the data files, users have to import OnedataFS libraries in the notebook and take advantage of the platform. Another approach would have been to use the oneclient module³¹ and mount the space as a local filesystem. This second approach requires more system privileges and appears more appropriate in the case of the remote desktop service developed in WP4 than in the case of a Jupyter notebook service.

A working example notebook where a user lists the content of a PaNOSC repository, access an HDF5 data file and saves back the plot obtained, is provided through the following link <https://github.com/EGI-Foundation/data-transfer-pilot/blob/master/hdf5.ipynb>.

```

In [6]: # Create connection to ONEPROVIDER_HOST
odfs = OnedataFS(os.environ['ONEPROVIDER_HOST'],
                 os.environ['ONECLIENT_ACCESS_TOKEN'],
                 force_proxy_io=True)

folder_name="samples/twinmic/"

# Set the path in OZ where the .h5 datasets is stored
OZ_path = os.path.join('/', space_name, folder_name)
print("\nDatasets path: %s" % OZ_path)

# Open remote dir
s1 = odfs.opendir(OZ_path)

# List contents from remote dir
s1.listdir('')

Datasets path: /PaNOSC/samples/twinmic/
Out[6]: ['twinmic_scan_41.h5']
  
```

Figure 6 Listing datasets in the volume

³¹ https://onedata.org/docs/doc/using_onedata/oneclient.html

5 Performance results

Due to the COVID-19 lockdown we limited the available bandwidth to 300Mbit/s to avoid impacting remote operation and business continuity of the RIs which are trying to offer remote experiments for researchers trying to understand the coronavirus mechanisms.

We will extend the test with other data providers in other RIs where we can use more bandwidth for a more comprehensive understanding of the limits of the current solution.

At the moment, we observed that the transfer of HDF5 data files with file size bigger than 200MB can reach the maximum bandwidth available. However smaller files have a much smaller throughputs ($\frac{1}{5}$), files of up to 50MB in size take the same amount of time of 250MB files, this seems to be due to the overhead required by the transfer protocol, this is a standard pattern of network file transfer protocols.

Figure 7 Onezone data transfer benchmark (Ceric-Eric -> CESNET)

For these tests the performance achieved is as good as the infrastructure has allowed, the transfer speed is close to the maximum network speed available for this pilot. It is nevertheless difficult to conclude definitively on the performance of the solution. In order to do this it will be required to extend the tests with RIs with more bandwidth capacity. This should happen once the lockdown of the major RIs will be lightened.

PaNOSC's WP6 will also need to perform acceptance tests by involving scientists and asking their feedback after they have performed real and comprehensive data analysis. To give an idea, with the current setup (bandwidth limited to 300Mb/s at the RI side) the impact of the initial data transfer (after this initial transfer, files are in cache) is 3mn to perform data analysis for a dataset of 4GB.

6 Conclusion

The solution implemented on the OneData framework is very promising, after being set up in the RIs it allows exposing a uniform interface for the users regardless of the location of the service and data. In the same interface, the user can access datasets archived in different RIs. It allows combining data from different facilities in a single analysis process. This is the same interface for all the data distributed across RIs' archive.

OneData provides the LUMA mechanism to perform the matching of the community userid that is used to perform the analyses (in our pilot through Jupyter notebooks) with the filesystem id owner, local to the RIs. This is an important feature for the community, in line with the current authorisation model. Unfortunately at the time of submitting this report LUMA was not successfully set up in our pilot, we are in contact with the OneData support team and expect to have it finalised in the coming weeks.

OneData is a solution in active development, the support team that we had contact with was extremely reactive and helped us to build the pilot.

We now need to expand the solution to more PaNOSC RIs and collect feedback from users. After this initial exploratory work, setting up the technical solution for a pilot in another RI is a matter of a few days of work, but more complex scenarios (data only available on tape systems for instance) might obviously require more important efforts.

This solution should also be explored with other analysis services like the remote desktop service.

7 Annex: implementation notes

Document Log

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Terminology

The EGI glossary of terms is available at: <https://wiki.egi.eu/wiki/Glossary>.

7.1 About this document

The present document is organized in four different sections:

- PART I: Provides guidelines on how to install and configure the OneZone service.
- PART II: Provides guidelines on how to install and configure the Oneprovider service.
- PART III: Outlines how to deploy a Kubernetes cluster with the EC3/IM.
- PART IV: Describes how to tailor the EGI Notebooks service to address the needs of the PaNOSC community.
- PART V: Described how to set-up a Binder instance for the project.

This document will be used by the PaN community to deploy the pilot in the different RIs. It is also expected to be used independently of this report by any other community having similar use cases.

7.2 Background information

There are three pilots use cases identified in the PaNOSC (WP6):

1. **Archiving use case:** Transfer data from a production RI to external cold storage. The volume of data is in the order of 300TB up to 10PB.
 - a. Initial data transfer tests between STFC and ILL are working.
 - i. FTS3 client and globus-url-copy
2. **Transfer of data to analysis services** provided by another organisation (e.g.: EGI). Typical scenario: a user wants to analyse datasets produced during one of the experiments in the EGI infrastructure using Jupyter notebooks service.
3. **User's data transfer:** an user wants to transfer datasets to his/her home PC. The PaNOSC community is interested in a solution which allows users to download GB to TB of datasets to their local computers. The solution has to be reliable and support different protocols (the http:// protocol is not reliable above a few GB). Some RIs of the PaNOSC community (e.g.: ESRF, DESY, EuXFEL, Diamond) are already familiar with the Globus online solution (free version), other RI facilities are planning to use this service in the near future. The volume of data involved in the data transfer is in the order of 100TB up to 10PB.

In this document we will focus on the technical requirements to set-up the pilot tested for supporting the second use case. For this pilot the following services/solutions will be used:

- [EGI Notebooks](#) service for supporting big data analytics,
- [Onedata](#) for federating data sets from the PaNOSC RIs, and
- [UmbrellaID](#) as Community proxy for the PaNOSC community.

7.2.1 The Onedata solution

Onedata is a global data management system, providing easy access to distributed storage resources, supporting a wide range of use cases from personal data management to data-intensive scientific computations.

7.2.2 Getting started

This section provides a quick overview of the [basic concepts](#) behind Onedata as well as [basic download](#) and [usage instructions](#).

7.2.3 Onedata for users

This section [explains](#) in more depth how to access, manage and share data using the Onedata platform.

7.2.4 Onedata for system administrators

This section describes how to deploy Onedata services, including Onezone for creating storage provider federations, as well as Oneprovider services to join existing Onezone federations and provide storage resources to users.

7.2.5 Onedata system requirements

Onedata services have certain minimum system requirements, which should be considered before deployment.

7.2.6 OneZone

Requirements	Minimal	Optimal
No. of VMs	1	2 + 1 for every 5000 users
CPU	8 vCPU cores	16 vCPU core
RAM	32 GB	64 GB
Local disk	SATA	SSD
Local storage space	20GB	40GB
OS (Docker deployment)	Any Docker compatible	Any Docker compatible
OS (Package deployment)	Ubuntu (16.04), CentOS 7	Ubuntu (16.04), CentOS 7

7.2.7 Oneprovider

Requirements	Minimal	Optimal
No. of VMs	1	2 + 1 for every 5000 users
CPU	8 vCPU cores	16 vCPU core
RAM	32 GB	64 GB
Local disk	SATA	SSD
Local storage space	20GB + 8MB for each 1000	40GB + 8MB for each 1000

	files	files
OS (Docker deployment)	Any Docker compatible	Any Docker compatible
OS (Package deployment)	Ubuntu (16.04), CentOS 7	Ubuntu (16.04), CentOS 7

Please note that these numbers are rough estimates and depend on actual data access patterns of users, network capacity and underlying storage performance.

7.3 PART I - Install and configure the OneZone service

To start to get familiar with the OneZone service, please refer to this [documentation](#). In this documentation we are going to install an instance of the OneZone service on a VM running with the following technical requirements:

OS	Ubuntu (bionic-x86_64)
Flavor	standard.2core-16ram (2 vCPU cores, 16GB of RAM and 80GB of local disk)
Hostname	onezone-panosc.egi.eu An entry for this hostname was registered in the DNS

7.3.1 Pre-requisites

In order to ensure optimum performance of the **Onezone** service, several low-level settings need to be tuned on the host machine. This applies to both Docker based as well as package based installations, in particular to nodes where Couchbase database instances are deployed. **After these settings are modified, the machine needs to be rebooted.**

7.3.2 Setting up certificates

Since release 18.02.0-rc10, Onezone supports automatic certificate management backed by Let's Encrypt. To use this option, it is only necessary to enable this feature in Onezone Docker Compose configuration file (see above) or via GUI. If you prefer to obtain and install certificates for Onezone service manually, modify the Docker Compose file to mount PEM files inside the container using paths listed in [TLS certificate management](#).

7.3.3 Firewall configuration in Onezone

Due to the fact that Onedata consists of several services which need to communicate between different sites, several ports need to be opened to the outside of the local network. Below is a detailed list of ports, which need to be opened and their designation in the Onezone service.

Port	Description
53/TCP	DNS (Required in Onezone)
53/UDP	DNS (Required in Onezone)
80/TCP	HTTP (Optional - automatically redirected to 443)
443/TCP	HTTPS, REST, Oneclient

7.3.4 Increase maximum number of opened files

In order to install **Onezone** service on one of the supported operating systems, first make sure that the maximum limit of opened files is sufficient (preferably 63536, but below `/proc/sys/fs/file-max`).

The limit can be checked using:

```
]$ ulimit -n 1024
```

If necessary, increase the limit using:

```
]$ sudo sh -c 'echo "* soft nofile 63536" >> /etc/security/limits.conf'  
]$ sudo sh -c 'echo "* hard nofile 63536" >> /etc/security/limits.conf'
```

It might be also necessary to setup the limit in `/etc/systemd/system.conf`:

```
]$ sudo sh -c 'echo DefaultLimitNOFILE=65536 >> /etc/systemd/system.conf'  
]$ sudo systemctl daemon-reexec
```

7.3.5 Disable systemd-resolved service

```
]$ sudo systemctl stop systemd-resolved  
]$ sudo systemctl disable systemd-resolved
```

7.3.6 Swap preference settings

Make sure that the swap preference (i.e. `swappiness`) is set to 0 (or at most 1 - see [here](#) for details):

```
]$ cat /proc/sys/vm/swappiness  
60
```

and if necessary decrease it using:

```
]$ sudo sh -c 'echo "vm.swappiness=0" >> /etc/sysctl.d/50-swappiness.conf'
```

7.3.7 Disable Transparent Huge Pages feature

By default, many Linux machines have the Transparent Huge Pages feature enabled, which improves apparent performance of machines running multiple applications at once, however it deteriorates the performance of most database-heavy applications, such as **Onezone**.

These settings can be checked using the following commands (here the output shown is the expected setting):

```
]$ cat /sys/kernel/mm/transparent_hugepage/enabled  
always madvise [never]
```

```
]$ cat /sys/kernel/mm/transparent_hugepage/defrag  
always madvise [never]
```

If any of the settings is different than the above, they should be changed permanently, which can be achieved for instance by creating a simple **systemd** unit file `/etc/systemd/system/disable-thp.service`:

```
[Unit]
```

```
Description=Disable Transparent Huge Pages
```

```
[Service]
```

```
Type=oneshot
```

```
ExecStart=/bin/sh -c "/bin/echo 'never' |
```

```
/usr/bin/tee/sys/kernel/mm/transparent_hugepage/enabled"
```

```
ExecStart=/bin/sh -c "/bin/echo 'never' |
```

```
/usr/bin/tee/sys/kernel/mm/transparent_hugepage/defrag"
```

[Install]

WantedBy=multi-user.target

and enabling it on start using:

```
]$ sudo systemctl enable disable-thp.service
```

```
]$ sudo systemctl start disable-thp.service
```

7.3.8 Increase network performance

By default, the Linux network stack is not configured for high speed large file transfer across WAN links. This is done to save memory resources. You can easily tune Linux network stack by increasing network buffers size for high-speed networks that connect server systems to handle more network packets.

Set the max OS send buffer size (wmem) and receive buffer size (rmem) to 16 MB for queues on all protocols. Add these settings in the `/etc/sysctl.conf` file:

```
]$ sysctl -w net.core.wmem_max=16777216
```

```
]$ sysctl -w net.core.rmem_max=16777216
```

Reboot the machine to make changes effective.

7.3.9 Setting the hostname

Make sure that the machine has a resolvable, domain-style hostname (it can be Fully Qualified Domain Name or just a proper entry in `/etc/hostname` and `/etc/hosts`) - for this tutorial it is set to `onezone-panosc.egi.eu`.

```
]$ cat /etc/hosts
```

```
127.0.0.1 onezone-panosc
```

```
# The following lines are desirable for IPv6 capable hosts
```

```
::1 ip6-localhost ip6-loopback
```

```
fe00::0 ip6-localnet
```

```
ff00::0 ip6-mcastprefix
```

```
ff02::1 ip6-allnodes
```

```
ff02::2 ip6-allrouters
```

```
ff02::3 ip6-allhosts
```

```
]$ cat /etc/hostname
```

```
onezone-panosc
```

Following command examples assumes an environment variable `ONEZONE_HOST` is available, for instance:

```
]$ export ONEZONE_HOST="onezone-panosc.egi.eu"
```

7.3.10 Python

Make sure that python 2.x is installed on the machine.

```
]$ python -V
```

```
Python 2.7.15+
```

7.3.11 Docker based setup

Onezone installation using Docker is very straightforward. This type of deployment requires that docker and docker-compose have been installed on your server.

7.3.12 Install Docker

```

]$ sudo apt install -y apt-transport-https \
    ca-certificates curl software-properties-common
]$ curl -fsSL https://download.docker.com/linux/ubuntu/gpg | sudo apt-key add -
]$ sudo add-apt-repository "deb [arch=amd64] https://download.docker.com/linux/ubuntu
    bionic stable"
]$ sudo apt update
]$ sudo apt install -y docker-ce
]$ sudo usermod -aG docker ${USER}

```

7.3.13 Install Docker Compose

```

]$ sudo curl -L https://github.com/docker/compose/releases/download/1.21.2/docker-compose-
    `uname -s`-`uname -m` -o /usr/local/bin/docker-compose
]$ sudo chmod +x /usr/local/bin/docker-compose

```

7.3.14 DNS records setup for subdomain delegation

Onezone has its own DNS server, automatically deployed on every node of the cluster. Its purpose is to simplify cluster scaling and allow for subdomain delegation for Oneproviders - i.e. allocating subdomains of the Onezone domain for the providers and resolving DNS queries in their name. In order for the subdomain delegation to work properly, it is necessary to set-up a DNS zone delegation in the DNS server responsible for your domain. It should delegate management of the Onezone domain and its subdomains to the Onezone DNS server.

Assuming your Onezone domain is `onezone-panosc.egi.eu.com` you need to set the following records at your DNS provider: NS records pointing to `ns1.onezone.org` and `ns2.onezone.org`, etc. Number of those subdomains depends on the number of nodes in your Onezone cluster. If there are more than 10 nodes, only the first ten should be inserted.

In the DNS responsible for the `onezone-panosc.egi.eu` domain (usually the server is administered by the domain provider, or there is a dedicated DNS server for your organization), set the following records:

Domain	Record	Value
<code>onezone-panosc.egi.eu.</code>	NS	<code>ns1.onezone-example.com.</code>
<code>onezone-panosc.egi.eu.</code>	NS	<code>ns2.onezone-example.com.</code>
<code>onezone-panosc.egi.eu.</code>	NS	<code>ns3.onezone-example.com.</code>
<code>ns1.onezone-example.com.</code>	A	<code>150.1.0.2</code>
<code>ns2.onezone-example.com.</code>	A	<code>150.1.0.3</code>
<code>ns3.onezone-example.com.</code>	A	<code>150.1.0.4</code>

This way, all queries concerning the `onezone-panosc.egi.eu` domain will be routed to the DNS servers running on Onezone cluster nodes.

7.3.15 Customizing Onezone Docker Compose script

In case of Docker based deployment all configuration information needed to install **Onezone** can be included directly in the Docker Compose script. This tutorial assumes that all **Onezone** configuration and log files will be stored in the folder `/opt/onedata/onezone` on the host machine, but you can use any directory to which Docker has access to. Make sure the partition where the `/opt` directory is mounted has at least 20GB of free space for logs and database files.

The following assumes you have prepared the following directory structure:

```
]$ sudo mkdir -p /opt/onedata/onezone
```

```
]$ sudo mkdir /opt/onedata/onezone/certs
```

```
]$ sudo mkdir /opt/onedata/onezone/persistence
```

Create the following Docker Compose file in `/opt/onedata/onezone/`

```
]$ sudo cat /opt/onedata/onezone/docker-compose.yml
```

```
version: '2'
```

```
networks:
```

```
  default:
```

```
    driver: bridge
```

```
    driver_opts:
```

```
      com.docker.network.driver.mtu: 1442
```

```
services:
```

```
  node1.onezone:
```

```
    restart: always
```

```
    image: onedata/onezone:19.02.1
```

```
    hostname: node1.onezone.local
```

```
    # dns: 8.8.8.8 # uncomment if container can't ping any domain
```

```
    container_name: onezone
```

```
    volumes:
```

```
      - "/var/run/docker.sock:/var/run/docker.sock"
```

```
      # Onezone persistence
```

```
      - "./data/persistence:/volumes/persistence"
```

```
      # Onezone config
```

```
      - "./data/configs/overlay.config:/etc/oz_worker/overlay.config"
```

```
      # OpenID & SAML config
```

```
      - "./data/secret/auth.config:/etc/oz_worker/auth.config"
```

```
      # Custom images used on the login page
```

```
      - "./data/images/umbrella.png:/var/www/html/oz_worker/custom/umbrella.png"
```

```
      - "./data/images/xdc.png:/var/www/html/oz_worker/custom/xdc.png"
```

```
      - "./data/images/deep.png:/var/www/html/oz_worker/custom/deep.png"
```

```
    ports:
```

```
      - "53:53"
```

```
      - "53:53/udp"
```

```
      - "80:80"
```

```
      - "443:443"
```

```
      - "9443:9443"
```

```
    environment:
```

```
      #ONEPANEL_DEBUG_MODE: "true" # prevents container exit on configuration error
```

```
      ONEPANEL_BATCH_MODE: "true"
```

```
      ONEPANEL_LOG_LEVEL: "none" # prints logs to stdout (possible values: none, debug, info, error), by default set to info
```

```
      ONEPANEL_EMERGENCY_PASSPHRASE: ${EMERGENCY_PASSPHRASE}
```

```

# Used for test purposes, disable when you have your own web cert mounted via volumes.
# Cert will be generated only if none is found under the cert path.
# If enabled, a new web cert will be generated with CN matching the
# ONEPANEL_GENERATED_CERT_DOMAIN and signed by OnedataTestWebServerCa
# NOTE: The generation will be performed upon every startup, any
# existing certs will be backed up and placed in the same directory.
# WARNING: This feature is devised for test purposes and must not
# be used in production.
ONEPANEL_GENERATE_TEST_WEB_CERT: "false" # default: false
# The generated test web cert will be issued for below domain.
ONEPANEL_GENERATED_CERT_DOMAIN: "" # default: ""
# If enabled, onepanel will trust any server that has a cert signed by
# the OnedataTestWebServerCa.
# WARNING: This feature is devised for test purposes and must not
# be used in production.
ONEPANEL_TRUST_TEST_CA: "false" # default: false
ONEZONE_CONFIG: |
cluster:
  domainName: "onezone-panosc.egi.eu"
  nodes:
    n1:
      hostname: "node1"
  managers:
    mainNode: "n1"
    nodes:
      - "n1"
  workers:
    nodes:
      - "n1"
  databases:
    nodes:
      - "n1"
  onezone:
    name: "PaNOSC"
    domainName: "onezone-panosc.egi.eu"
    letsEncryptEnabled: true

```

To enable federated authentication mechanism and local access, update the `/opt/onedata/onezone/data/secret/auth.config` file with the settings:

```

#{
  version => 3,
  % Allows to log in to Onezone using username & password.
  basicAuthConfig => #{
    enabled => true
  },
  openidConfig => #{
    % Enable OpenID login protocol - if disabled, all OpenID IdPs will be
    % hidden from the login page.
    enabled => true,

```

```
[..]
},
supportedIdps => [
  {basicAuth, #{
    % Configuration of the login page button
    displayName => "username & password",
    % Some predefined icons are built-in into the GUI app.
    % Their paths start with /assets/images/auth-providers.
    % For a custom icon, put it in:
    % /var/www/html/oz_worker/custom/<path>
    % And reference it here like this: /custom/<path>
    iconPath => "/assets/images/auth-providers/basicauth.svg",
    % Background color is useful for icons with transparency. Moreover,
    % after selecting an IdP, its icon disappears and a spinner is
    % shown - hence background color should be kept the same as icon's
    % background color (if any).
    iconBackgroundColor => "#4BD187",
    % Which protocol is used for this IdP - basicAuth is the only
    % valid one for basicAuth IdP.
    protocol => basicAuth
  }},
},
```

In this configuration the OpenID setting has been used to enable UmbrellaID as community proxy service for the PaNOSC community. Additional AAI providers can also be included in the configuration if needed.

```
{UmbrellaID, #{
  displayName => "UmbrellaID",
  iconPath => "/custom/umbrella.png",
  iconBackgroundColor => "#0455A1",
  protocol => openid,
  protocolConfig => #{
    plugin => default_oidc_plugin,
    pluginConfig => #{
      clientId => "XXX-XXXXXXXX-XXXX-XXXX-XXXX-XXXXXXXXXXXXXXXX",
      clientSecret => "XXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXX",
      endpoints => #{
        xrds => "https://proxy.umbrellaid.org/well-known/openid-configuration",
        authorize => {xrds, "authorization_endpoint"},
        accessToken => {xrds, "token_endpoint"},
        userInfo => {xrds, "userinfo_endpoint"}
      },
      scope => "openid email profile",
      accessTokenAcquireMethod => post,
      clientSecretPassMethod => urlencoded,
      accessTokenPassMethod => urlencoded
    }
  }
}
}}
```

```
]
}.
```

7.3.16 Custom icon guidelines

To use your custom icon on the login page, place it on the Onezone host under the path `/var/www/html/oz_worker/custom/<path>` and reference it in the config like this: `iconPath => "/custom/<path>".` If you are using docker-compose, simply mount your icon by adding a volume, for example:

```
]$ cat docker-compose.yaml
[.]
  volumes:
    - "/path/to/your/icon.svg:/var/www/html/oz_worker/custom/my-icon.svg"
```

To obtain the best visual effects, please check the online documentation available [here](#).

7.3.17 Install Docker images

To install the necessary Docker images on the machine run:

```
]$ cd /opt/onedata/onezone
]$ docker-compose -f /opt/onedata/onezone/docker-compose.yml pull
```

7.3.18 Start OneZone

```
]$ cd /opt/onedata/onezone
]$ ./onezone.sh start
Pulling node1.onezone (docker.onedata.org/onezone:19.02.1)...
[.]
Creating network "onezone_default" with the default driver
Creating onezone ... done
```

7.3.19 Checking Logs

```
]$ ./onezone.sh logs
Copying missing persistent files...
Done.
Starting oz_panel...
[ OK ] oz_panel started
Waiting for the existing cluster to start...
Existing Onezone deployment resumed work.
```

Container details:

```
* IP Address: 172.18.0.2
* Ports: -
```

```
]$ ./onezone panel-logs
[.]
"Node 'cluster_manager@node1.onezone.local' not responding to pings."
[E 2019-11-27 15:13:41.071 <0.521.0>] Command "service couchbase-server status" exited
with code 3 and output
" * couchbase-server is not running"
```


[.]

[I 2019-11-27 15:14:28.047 <0.864.0>] Setting up Onezone panel service in Onezone

[I 2019-11-27 15:14:28.210 <0.864.0>] Deployed static GUI files
(7c7c3aa91c703bf38397f42fd51f2b0a73d992160be2c92e65a2d24546900a9a)

[I 2019-11-27 15:14:28.220 <0.864.0>] **Onezone panel service successfully set up in Onezone**

7.3.20 Configure the volume space in OneZone

Open [https://\\$ONEZONE_HOST:9443](https://$ONEZONE_HOST:9443) using any web browser and continue through the steps described [here](#). After this step succeeds, Onezone should be ready and accessible at [https://\\$ONEZONE_HOST](https://$ONEZONE_HOST).

7.4 PART II - Install and configure the Oneprovider services

To start to get familiar with the Oneprovider service, please refer to this [documentation](#). In this documentation we are going to install Oneprovider service at CESNET-MCC and two Oneprovider services at CERIC-ERIC on VMs having the following technical requirements:

OS	Ubuntu (bionic-x86_64)
Flavor	hpc.16cores-32ram (16 vCPU cores, 32GB of RAM and 80GB of local disk)
Storage	An additional block storage of 800GB is mounted in /mnt
Hostname	oneprovider-pn-cesnet
Location	CESNET

OS	Ubuntu (bionic-x86_64)
Flavor	hpc.16cores-32ram (16 vCPU cores, 32GB of RAM and 120GB of local virtio disk)
Storage	An additional NFS volume storage of 1024GB is mounted in /mnt
Hostname	oneprovider-pn-ceric
Location	CERIC-ERIC

OS	Ubuntu (bionic-x86_64)
Flavor	hpc.16cores-32ram (16 vCPU cores, 32GB of RAM and 120GB of local virtio disk)
Storage	Only local, 120gb virtio disk
Hostname	ceric-op-cache
Location	CERIC-ERIC

7.4.1 Pre-requisites

Oneprovider machines (if the deployment is dockerized - dockers too) require the following parameters set for network buffers:

```
sysctl -w net.core.wmem_max=16777216
sysctl -w net.core.rmem_max=16777216
```

7.4.2 Setting up certificates

Since release 18.02.0-beta5, Oneprovider supports automatic certificate management backed by Let's Encrypt. To use this option, it is only necessary to enable this feature in Oneprovider Docker Compose configuration file (see above) or via GUI.

If you prefer to obtain and install certificates for Oneprovider service manually, modify the Docker Compose file to mount PEM files inside the container using paths listed in [TLS certificate management](#).

7.4.3 Firewall configuration in Oneprovider

Oneprovider requires the following ports to be opened:

Port	Description
80/TCP	HTTP (Optional - automatically redirected to 443)
443/TCP	HTTPS, REST, Oneclient
6665/TCP	Onedata data transfer channel (Oneprovider RTransfer)
9443/TCP	Onepanel web interface (can be limited to local network)

7.4.4 Deploy the Oneprovider server

The easiest way to deploy Oneprovider is using Onedatify. To generate the online Onedatify command in Onezone:

- Go to Onezone interface,
- Select Add support... option under the space name, and
- Select the tab Expose existing data set:

The screenshot shows the Onezone interface with a sidebar on the left containing navigation options like 'Overview', 'Providers', and 'Members'. The main content area is titled 'ADD SUPPORT' and has three tabs: 'Request support', 'Deploy your own Oneprovider', and 'Expose existing data set'. The 'Expose existing data set' tab is active, showing instructions to deploy the service and expose storage with existing data. It includes a diagram of a folder pointing to a server icon, which then points to a cloud icon. Below this, it lists supported Linux distributions: Ubuntu 16.04, 18.04, Debian 9, and CentOS 7. At the bottom, there is a 'Command' section with a long curl command for registration.

7.4.5 CESNET Oneprovider deployment via onedatify

Run the command on the target node:

```
]$ curl https://get.onedata.org/onedatify.sh | sh -s onedatify \  
--onezone-url 'https://onezone-panosc.egi.eu\  
--registration-token 'MDAxNWxvY2F00[..]8YKDdNCpy8Hd9bOrUF' \  
--token 'MDAxNWxvY2F00[..]8YKDdNCpy8Hd9bOrUF' --import  
[.]
```

Downloaded Onedatify installation script /tmp/onedatify_19.02.1.rc2.sh

The Onedatify script allows you to easily install Oneprovider service and connect to an existing data space.

This script will perform following changes on this machine:

- install the latest versions of Docker and Docker Compose
- change machine 'ulimit' to the value found in /proc/sys/fs/file-max
- disable swappiness and Transparent Huge Pages feature
- open all ports required by Oneprovider

Oneprovider requires valid SSL certificates

to register with Onezone, you can provide your own certificates

or Onedatify script will help you generate Let's Encrypt certificates.

In order to install Onedatify service prepare the following items:

- a fully qualified domain name (FQDN) of this machine
- an operating system that supports systemd
- the following ports need to be open:

80/TCP HTTP

443/TCP HTTPS

6665/TCP Onedata data transfer channel (RTransfer)

9443/TCP Onepanel web interface - needed only for system administrators

If you want to expose existing data via Onedata,

the storage with the data must be accessible for this machine through a POSIX path (e.g. NFS mount point).

If you expect this provider to transfer data to other providers, make sure that this VM has a direct connection (public IP or dedicated routing), to other providers you want to transfer data to.

Are you ready to proceed with the installation (y|n)?: **y**

[.]

Installing Onedatify Package

Onedatify installation process started...

Docker installation found.

Docker-compose binary was detected on the machine.

Installing onedatify package:

onedatify 19.02.1.rc2.systemd

Reading package lists... Done

Building dependency tree

Reading state information... Done

The following package was automatically installed and is no longer required:

Grub-pc-bin

Use 'sudo apt autoremove' to remove it.

The following packages will be REMOVED:

```

Onedatify
The following held packages will be changed:
Onedatify
0 upgraded, 0 newly installed, 1 to remove and 99 not upgraded.
[.]
(Reading database ... 90871 files and directories currently installed.)
Preparing to unpack .../onedatify_19.02.1.rc2.systemd_amd64.tGHcNNO.deb ...
Unpacking onedatify (19.02.1.rc2.systemd) over (19.02.1.rc2.systemd) ...
Setting up onedatify (19.02.1.rc2.systemd) ...
onedatify set on hold.
#####
Package installation successful.
onedata/oneprovider:19.02.1-rc2

#####
version=onedata/oneprovider:19.02.1-rc2
zone_fqdn=onezone-panosc.egi.eu
admin_password=*****
admin_email=giuseppe.larocca@egi.eu
name=cesnet
fqdn=cesnet-op.onezone-panosc.egi.eu
persistence_volume=/opt/onedata/onedatify/oneprovider_conf
overlay_panel_volume=/opt/onedata/onedatify/op-panel-overlay.config
overlay_worker_volume=/opt/onedata/onedatify/op-worker-overlay.config
subdomain=cesnet-op
domain_name=onezone-panosc.egi.eu
onezone_registration_token=MDAyM2xvY[.]rhBfIQWt00vt1qeq8YKDdNCpy8Hd9bOrUFLvFQC
g
subdomain_delegation=true
lets_encrypt_enabled=true
key=
cert=
cacert=
extra_cacerts=
geo_latitude=50.10496139526367
geo_longitude=14.382089614868164
#####

```

You will now be asked to provide configuration parameters:

```

##### Basic parameters #####
Please enter the pretty name of your oneprovider (default: cesnet):
Enter a new administration password for the Oneprovider or the password will be auto
generated:
Your new password to login into Oneprovider is: *****
Please enter the email address that will be used as the emergency contact for this provider
(default: giuseppe.larocca@egi.eu): <ENTER>
Absolute path where to keep oneprovider configuration and metadata (default:
/opt/onedata/onedatify/oneprovider_conf): <ENTER>
Please enter the latitude of your provider (auto-detected default: 50.10496139526367):

```


<ENTER>

Please enter the longitude of your provider (auto-detected default: 14.382089614868164):

<ENTER>

Certificates

You can choose to provide your own certificates or use subdomain delegation and request Onezone to help in generating the Let's Encrypt certificate for your subdomain.

Do you want to use a subdomain delegation to acquire a FQDN for your Oneprovider? (y/n, default: y)?: **y**

Please enter the subdomain for your oneprovider (auto-detected default: oneprovider-pn):

cesnet-op

The FQDN of your Oneprovider is: **cesnet-op.onezone-panosc.egi.eu**

Do you want Onezone to create a Let's Encrypt certificate for Oneprovider (y/n, default: y)? **y**

INFO: Let's Encrypt allows you to create only 5 duplicate certificates per week! Use this option with care!

Storage Configuration

What storage type would you like to use? (default: posix, possible options: posix | s3 | ceph | glusterfs | swift): **posix**

An absolute path to a directory you want to expose trough Onedata from POSIX storage (default: /tmp): **/mnt**

Please provide the url to the LUMA server, or leave it blank:

Expose storage as read only? (y/n, default: n): **n**

Created symlink /etc/systemd/system/multi-user.target.wants/onedatify.service → /usr/lib/systemd/system/onedatify.service.

Starting Oneprovider

Installation is about to start, you can observe detailed logs by executing following command in a second window:

onedatify logs

Waiting for oneprovider to start.....

Congratulations! Oneprovider has started successfully.

The size of space support (you can use B, KiB, MiB, up to EiB, 1KiB = 1024B, eg. 1GiB) (auto-detected: 786.4477GiB): <ENTER>

Supporting a space with ***** [B] of storage onedatify on oneprovider oneprovider-pn.onezone-panosc.egi.eu

Checking Oneprovider readiness..

Your storage was successfully supported and exposed.

Depending on the amount of exposed data it might take some time to scan it. Please be patient.

To configure your Oneprovider please visit:

<https://oneprovider-pn.onezone-panosc.egi.eu:9443>

In order to access your data please visit:

<https://onezone-panosc.egi.eu>

Generated password to access the Onepanel emergency account is: *****

7.4.6 CERIC-ERIC Oneprovider deployment

```

]$ curl https://get.onedata.org/onedatify.sh | sh -s onedatify --onezone-url 'https://onezone-panosc.egi.eu' --registration-token 'MDAyM2xvY2F[.]02LvHtLaEyKE2njnEDI015Cg' --token 'MDAyM2xvY2F00aW[.]' --import
[.]

```

In order to install Onedatify service prepare the following items:

- a fully qualified domain name (FQDN) of this machine
- an operating system that supports systemd
- **the following ports need to be open:**
 - 80/TCP HTTP**
 - 443/TCP HTTPS**
 - 6665/TCP Onedata data transfer channel (RTransfer)**
 - 9443/TCP Onepanel web interface - needed only for system administrators**

If you want to expose existing data via Onedata, the storage with the data must be accessible for this machine through a POSIX path (e.g. NFS mount point).

If you expect this provider to transfer data to other providers, make sure that this VM has a direct connection (public IP or dedicated routing), to other providers you want to transfer data to.

Are you ready to proceed with the installation (y|n)?: y

[.]

Installing Onedatify Package

Onedatify installation process started...

Docker installation found.

Docker-compose binary was detected on the machine.

Installing onedatify package:

```
onedatify 19.02.1.systemd
```

[...]

Preparing to unpack .../onedatify_19.02.1.systemd_amd64.bRjByY0.deb ...

Unpacking onedatify (19.02.1.systemd) over (19.02.1.systemd) ...

Setting up onedatify (19.02.1.systemd) ...

onedatify set on hold.

#####

Package installation successful.

```
onedata/oneprovider:19.02.1
```

[...]

#####

You will now be asked to provide configuration parameters:

Basic parameters

Please enter the name of your oneprovider (default: ceric): **ceric**

Enter a new administration password for the Oneprovider or the password will be auto generated:

Your new password to login into Oneprovider is: *****

Please enter the email address that will be used as the emergency contact for this provider :

marco.desimone@elettra.eu

Absolute path where to keep oneprovider configuration and metadata (default:

/opt/onedata/onedatify/oneprovider_conf):

Please enter the latitude of your provider (auto-detected default: 45.662498474121094):
Please enter the longitude of your provider (auto-detected default: 13.797300338745117):

Certificates

You can choose to provide your own certificates or use subdomain delegation and request Onezone to help in generating the Let's Encrypt certificate for your subdomain.

Do you want to use a subdomain delegation to acquire a FQDN for your Oneprovider? (y/n, default: y)?: **y**

Please enter the subdomain for your oneprovider (auto-detected default: ceric-op): The FQDN of your Oneprovider is: **ceric-op.onezone-panosc.egi.eu**

Storage Configuration

What storage type would you like to use? (default: posix, possible options: posix | s3 | ceph | glusterfs | swift): **posix**

An absolute path to a directory you want use to support your Onedata POSIX storage (default: /tmp): **/mnt/ceric-datasets**

Created symlink /etc/systemd/system/multi-user.target.wants/onedatify.service → /usr/lib/systemd/system/onedatify.service.

Starting Oneprovider

Installation is about to start, you can observe detailed logs by executing following command in a second window: onedatify logs

Waiting for oneprovider to start.....

Congratulations! Oneprovider has started successfully.

The size of space support (you can use B, KiB, MiB, up to EiB, 1KiB = 1024B, eg. 1GiB) (auto-detected: 1023.1768GiB):

Supporting a space with 1098627678208 [B] of storage onedatify on oneprovider ceric-op.onezone-panosc.egi.eu

Checking Oneprovider readiness..

Your storage was successfully supported and exposed.

Depending on the amount of exposed data it might take some time to scan it. Please be patient.

To configure your Oneprovider please visit:

<https://ceric-op.onezone-panosc.egi.eu:9443>

In order to access your data please visit:

<https://onezone-panosc.egi.eu>

Generated password to access the Onepanel emergency account is: *****

7.4.7 CERIC op-cache

```

]$ curl https://get.onedata.org/onedatify.sh | sh -s onedatify --onezone-url 'https://onezone-panosc.egi.eu' --registration-token 'MDAyM2xvY2F00aW[.]0SKcvuXXIQMGNKJWIGTaZ9bZCg' --token 'MDAyM2xvY2F00aW9uIG9uZ[.]b31xX2jUT8DsCyYoQo' --import [...]

```

Basic parameters

Please enter the name of your oneprovider (default: ceric-op-cache): **ceric-cache**

Enter a new administration password for the Oneprovider or the password will be auto generated:

Your new password to login into Oneprovider is: *****

Please enter the email address that will be used as the emergency contact for this provider (default: marco.desimone@elettra.eu): **<ENTER>**

Absolute path where to keep oneprovider configuration and metadata (default: /opt/onedata/onedatify/oneprovider_conf): **<ENTER>**

Please enter the latitude of your provider (auto-detected default: 45.662498474121094):
<ENTER>

Please enter the longitude of your provider (auto-detected default: 13.797300338745117):
<ENTER>

Certificates

You can choose to provide your own certificates or use subdomain delegation and request Onezone to help in generating the Let's Encrypt certificate for your subdomain.

Do you want to use a subdomain delegation to acquire a FQDN for your Oneprovider? (y/n, default: y): **y**

Please enter the subdomain for your oneprovider (auto-detected default: oneprovider-pn-ceric-cache): **ceric-cache**

The FQDN of your Oneprovider is: ceric-cache.onezone-panosc.eji.eu

Storage Configuration

What storage type would you like to use? (default: posix, possible options: posix | s3 | ceph | glusterfs | swift): **posix**

An absolute path to a directory you want to expose through Onedata from POSIX storage (default: /tmp): **/cache**

Please provide the url to the LUMA server, or leave it blank: <ENTER>

Expose storage as read only? (y/n, default: n): **n**

Created symlink /etc/systemd/system/multi-user.target.wants/onedatify.service → /usr/lib/systemd/system/onedatify.service.

Starting Oneprovider

Installation is about to start, you can observe detailed logs by executing following command in a second window:

```
onedatify logs
```

Waiting for oneprovider to start.....

Congratulations! Oneprovider has started successfully.

The size of space support (you can use B, KiB, MiB, up to EiB, 1KiB = 1024B, eg. 1GiB) (auto-detected: 117.6148GiB): <ENTER>

Do you want to regularly scan storage for any changes in files? (y/n, default: y): **y**

Supporting a space with 126287937536 [B] of storage onedatify on oneprovider ceric-cache.onezone-panosc.eji.eu

Checking Oneprovider readiness..

Your storage was successfully supported and exposed.

Depending on the amount of exposed data it might take some time to scan it. Please be patient.

To configure your Oneprovider please visit:

<https://ceric-cache.onezone-panosc.eji.eu:9443>

In order to access your data please visit:

<https://onezone-panosc.eji.eu>

Generated password to access the Onepanel emergency account is:

7.4.8 CERIC-ERIC notes

There's a small bug in the onedatify script, it does not accept domain name with a dash symbol (ceric-eric.eu) so I had to use elettra.eu domain and then fix the web gui once the oneprovider was online, the issue has been submitted to onedata developers.

The two CERIC-ERIC oneproviders are located in the Elettra's DMZ lan, they have internal IP addresses and there is a reverse 1to1 public NAT for both, it is managed by a sonic-wall firewall, their FQDN is associated with their public IP address:

- ceric-op.onezone-panosc.egi.eu -> 140.105.207.31 <-> 172.19.31.6
- ceric-cache.onezone-panosc.egi.eu -> 140.105.207.32 <-> 172.19.31.7

Since they cannot use the public ip address to connect to each other and also to improve the network performance, the /etc/hosts files on both machine have been modified as follow, in order to force to use the internal lan (25Gbit):

```
127.0.0.1    localhost
172.19.31.6 ceric-op.onezone-panosc.egi.eu
172.19.31.6 oneprovider-pn.ceric-eric.eu oneprovider-pn
172.19.31.7 ceric-cache.onezone-panosc.egi.eu
172.19.31.7 op-cache-01.ceric-eric.eu op-cache-01 ceric-cache
```

7.5 PART III - Create a K8s cluster with EC3

In this section it will be described how a Kubernetes (K8s) virtual cluster composed by 1 master node and 2 workers is configured to spawn Jupyter notebooks on demand for users. For the configuration of the K8s cluster it will be used the [Elastic Cloud Compute Cluster \(EC3\)](#) framework developed by the [Polytechnic University of Valencia \(UPV\)](#).

7.5.1 Configure the environment

EC3 has an official Docker container image available in Docker Hub that can be used instead of installing the CLI. You can download it by typing:

```
]$ sudo docker pull grycap/ec3
```

7.5.2 Listing available EC3 templates

To list the available templates, use the command:

```
]$ cd $HOME
]$ sudo docker run -v /tmp/ec3/clusters:/root/.ec3/clusters grycap/ec3 templates
```

name	summary
blcr	Tool for checkpoint applications
bowtie2	Fast and sensitive read alignment
centos-ec2	CentOS 6.5 amd64 on EC2
chronos	An open-source tool to orchestrate job execution in a Mesos cluster

ckptman Tool to automatically checkpoint applications running on Spot Instances

consul Service Discovery and Configuration Made Easy

docker An open-source tool to deploy applications inside software Containers

docker-compose A tool for defining and running multi-container Docker applications

kubefaaS Install FaaS frameworks in a kubernetes cluster

kubernetes Install and configure a cluster using the grycap.kubernetes ansible role [..]

7.5.3 Listing running clusters

To list the running clusters, use the command:

```
]$ cd $HOME
]$ sudo docker run -v /tmp/ec3/clusters:/root/.ec3/clusters grycap/ec3 list
```

```
name      state      IP          nodes
-----
cluster   configured 212.189.145.XXX 0
```

7.5.4 Authorization file

The authorization file stores in plain text the credentials to access the cloud providers, the IM service and the VMRC service. Each line of the file is composed of pairs of key and value separated by semicolon, and refers to a single credential. The key and value should be separated by "=", that is **an equal sign preceded and followed by one white space at least**.

E.g.: Creation of an auth file to use OIDC token.

```
]$ cat auth_OIDC_CESNET-MCC_K8s.dat
id = cesnetostegi; type = OpenStack; host = https://identity.cloud.muni.cz; username = egi.eu;
tenant = openid; domain = panosc.eu; auth_version = 3.x_oidc_access_token; password =
'XXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXX'
```

The Keystone Identity URL for the cloud provider can be retrieved from the EGI [GOCDB](#).

7.5.5 Templates to configure the K8s cluster

The K8s virtual cluster will be configured with the following templates:

- **kubernetes (default template)**
- **ubuntu-1604-OIDC-CESNET_K8s (custom template)**
- **configure_nfs (custom template)**
- **refreshtoken (custom template)**

Custom templates are stored in the \$HOME/ec3/templates.

7.5.6 Templates used to configure the K8s cluster

This section contains the templates used to configure the cluster.

Cluster_configure.radl

```

]$ cat ec3/templates/configure_nfs.radl
# http://www.server-world.info/en/note?os=CentOS\_6&p=nfs&f=1
# http://www.server-world.info/en/note?os=CentOS\_7&p=nfs
description nfs (
  kind = 'component' and
  short = 'Tool to configure shared directories inside a network.' and
  content = 'Network File System (NFS) client allows you to access shared directories from Linux
client. This recipe installs nfs from the repository and shares the /home/ubuntu directory with all
the nodes that compose the cluster.
Webpage: http://www.grycap.upv.es/clues/'
)
network public (
  outports contains '111/tcp' and
  outports contains '111/udp' and
  outports contains '2046/tcp' and
  outports contains '2046/udp' and
  outports contains '2047/tcp' and
  outports contains '2047/udp' and
  outports contains '2048/tcp' and
  outports contains '2048/udp' and
  outports contains '2049/tcp' and
  outports contains '2049/udp' and
  outports contains '892/tcp' and
  outports contains '892/udp' and
  outports contains '32803/tcp' and
  outports contains '32769/udp'
)
system front (
  ec3_templates contains 'nfs' and
  disk.0.applications contains (name = 'ansible.modules.grycap.nfs')
)
configure front (
@begin
  - roles:
    - { role: 'grycap.nfs', nfs_mode: 'front', nfs_exports: [{path: "/home", export:
"wn*.localdomain(rw,async,no_root_squash,no_subtree_check,insecure)"}] }
@end
)
system wn ( ec3_templates contains 'nfs' )
configure wn (
@begin
  - roles:
    - { role: 'grycap.nfs', nfs_mode: 'wn', nfs_client_imports: [{ local: "/home",
remote: "/home", server_host: '{{
hostvars[groups["front"][0]]["IM_NODE_PRIVATE_IP"] }}' ] }
@end
)
include nfs_misc (
  template = 'openports'

```

```
)  
ubuntu-1604-OIDC-CESNET_K8s.radi  
  
description ubuntu-1604-occi-CESNET (  
  kind = 'images' and  
  short = 'Ubuntu 16.04' and  
  content = 'Image for EGI Ubuntu 16.04 LTS [Ubuntu/16.04/KVM]'  
)  
network public (  
  provider_id = 'public-cesnet-78-128-251-GROUP' and  
  outports contains '443/tcp' and  
  outports contains '80/tcp'  
)  
network private (provider_id = 'auto_allocate_network')  
  
system front (  
  cpu.arch = 'x86_64' and  
  cpu.count >= 8 and  
  memory.size >= 16384m and  
  disk.0.os.name = 'linux' and  
  # PaNOSC tenant  
  disk.0.image.url = 'ost://identity.cloud.muni.cz/e8d75fc1-ac32-4851-90b5-b4c925e9e6f8'  
and  
  disk.0.os.credentials.username = 'ubuntu'  
)  
system wn (  
  cpu.arch = 'x86_64' and  
  cpu.count >= 8 and  
  memory.size >= 16384m and  
  ec3_max_instances = 5 and # maximum number of working nodes in the cluster  
  disk.0.os.name = 'linux' and  
  # PaNOSC tenant  
  disk.0.image.url = 'ost://identity.cloud.muni.cz/e8d75fc1-ac32-4851-90b5-b4c925e9e6f8'  
and  
  disk.0.os.credentials.username = 'ubuntu'  
)  
  
refreshtoken.radi  
  
description refreshtoken (  
  kind = 'component' and  
  short = 'Tool to refresh LToS access token.' and  
  content = 'Tool to refresh LToS access token.'  
)  
configure front (  
@begin  
  - vars:  
    CLIENT_ID: ef4d5286-0db3-4c06-87ff-6a27ec97cb85  
    CLIENT_SECRET: O-...5KJwrm-UzHJK_4Z5tfyKF5RbtbluJcnzeGzPz8xmlfbCWEjKjDj_aBT3HlIA
```

```

REFRESH_TOKEN_FILE:
  ec3_file: refresh_token.py
Tasks:
- name: Create dir /usr/local/ec3/
  file: path=/usr/local/ec3/ state=directory
- copy:
  dest: /usr/local/ec3/refresh_token.py
  content: "{{REFRESH_TOKEN_FILE}}"
  mode: 0700
- cron:
  name: "refresh token"
  minute: "*/5"
  job: "[ -f /usr/local/ec3/auth.dat ] && /usr/local/ec3/refresh_token.py {{ CLIENT_ID }} {{
CLIENT_SECRET }}"
  user: root
  cron_file: refresh_token
  state: present
@end
)

```

The [refresh_token.py](#) has to be copied in the \$HOME/ec3/templates.

7.5.7 Create a K8s cluster

To create a K8s cluster, use the command:

```

]# sudo docker run -v /home/centos:/tmp/ \
-v /home/centos/ec3/templates:/root/.ec3/templates \
-v /tmp/.ec3/clusters:/root/.ec3/clusters grycap/ec3 launch k8s_cluster \
kubernetes ubuntu-1604-OIDC-CESNET_K8s configure_nfs refreshtoken \
-a /tmp/auth_OIDC_CESNET-MCC_K8s.dat
Creating infrastructure
Infrastructure successfully created with ID:
b5a86286-3e93-11ea-9f7c-fae41df0e987
Front-end state: launching
Front-end state: pending,
IP: NoneFront-end state: running,
IP: NoneFront-end state: running, IP: XXX.XXX.XXX.XXX
Front-end configured with IP XXX.XXX.XXX.XXX
Transferring infrastructure
Front-end ready!

```

7.5.8 Access the K8s cluster

To access the configured K8s cluster, use the command:

```

]# cd $HOME
]# sudo docker run -ti -v /tmp/.ec3/clusters:/root/.ec3/clusters grycap/ec3 ssh k8s_cluster
[.]
Use the clues daemon to start workers in the K8s cluster:

```

```
]$ clues poweron wn1.localdomain wn2.localdomain
```

```
[..]
```

Use the `is_cluster_ready` CLI to check the status of the cluster. When the cluster is configured change the status of the workers to prevent clues shutdowns the sites when idle:

```
]$ clues disable wn1.localdomain wn2.localdomain
```

```
]$ clues status
```

```
node      state enabled  time stable  (cpu,mem) used  (cpu,mem) total
-----
wn1.localdomain  used disabled 21h06'28"  0.55,1394606080 8,16713998336
wn2.localdomain  used disabled 21h06'28"  0.15,320864256  8,16714006528
wn3.localdomain  off  enabled 21h37'20"  0,0          1,1073741824
[..]
```

7.5.9 Listing running EC3 clusters

To list running clusters, use the command:

```
]$ cd $HOME
```

```
]$ sudo docker run -v /tmp/.ec3/clusters:/root/.ec3/clusters grycap/ec3 list
```

```
  name      state  IP      nodes
-----
k8s_cluster configured XXX.XXX.XXX.XXX 0
```

7.5.10 Destroy the EC3 cluster

To destroy the configured K8s cluster, use the command:

```
]$ cd $HOME
```

```
]$ sudo docker run -ti -v /tmp/.ec3/clusters:/root/.ec3/clusters grycap/ec3 destroy k8s_cluster
```

```
WARNING: you are going to delete the infrastructure (including frontend and nodes).
```

```
Continue [y/N]? Y
```

```
Success deleting the cluster!
```

7.6 PART IV - Configure the K8s cluster to spawn Jupyter notebooks

A Kubernetes cluster deployed into a cloud resource provider is in charge of managing the containers that will provide the service. On this cluster there are:

- 1 master node that manages the whole cluster;
- Support for load balancer or alternatively 1 or more edge nodes with a public IP and corresponding public DNS name (e.g. notebooks.egi.eu) where a k8s ingress HTTP reverse proxy redirects requests from users to other components of the service. The HTTP server has a valid certificate from one CA recognised at most browsers (e.g. Let's Encrypt).
- 1 or more nodes that host the JupyterHub server, the notebooks servers where the users will run their notebooks. The JupyterHub is deployed using the [JupyterHub helm charts](#). These nodes should have enough capacity to run as many concurrent user notebooks as needed. Main constraint is usually memory.
- Support for [Kubernetes PersistentVolumeClaims](#) for storing the persistent folders. Default EGI-Notebooks installation uses NFS, but any other volume type with ReadWriteOnce capabilities can be used.

7.6.1 Configure the volume space in the K8s master node

Access the K8s master node and change the settings in the /etc/exports

```
]$ mkdir /volumes
]$ /home wn*.localdomain(rw,async,no_root_squash,no_subtree_check,insecure)
/volumes                               wn*.localdomain(rw,no_root_squash,no_subtree_check)
kubeserver.localdomain(rw,no_root_squash,no_subtree_check)
```

```
]$ exportfs -ra
]$ sudo exportfs
/volumes    kubeserver.localdomain
/home       wn*.localdomain
/volumes    wn*.localdomain
```

Check the status of the K8s cluster:

```
]$ kubectl get nodes
NAME                STATUS  ROLES  AGE  VERSION
kubeserver.localdomain Ready  master  14m  v1.15.7
wn1.localdomain     Ready  <none>  4m21s v1.15.7
wn2.localdomain     Ready  <none>  4m16s v1.15.7
```

7.6.2 Helm

Install Helm in the K8s master node:

```
]$ wget https://get.helm.sh/helm-v3.0.2-linux-amd64.tar.gz
]$ tar zxf helm-v3.0.2-linux-amd64.tar.gz
]$ cd linux-amd64
```

```
]$ sudo mv helm /usr/local/bin/helm
]$ helm version
version.BuildInfo{Version:"v3.0.2",
GitCommit:"19e47ee3283ae98139d98460de796c1be1e3975f",      GitTreeState:"clean",
GoVersion:"go1.13.5"}
```

7.6.3 nfs-provider

Install the nfs-provider in the K8s master node:

```
]$ sudo helm repo add stable https://kubernetes-charts.storage.googleapis.com
"stable" has been added to your repositories
```

```
]$ sudo helm repo update
Hang tight while we grab the latest from your chart repositories...
...Successfully got an update from the "stable" chart repository
Update Complete. * Happy Helming!*
```

```
]$ sudo helm install nfs-provisioner stable/nfs-client-provisioner \
  --namespace kube-system \
  --set nfs.server=192.168.8.57 \
  --set storageClass.defaultClass=true \
  --set nfs.path=/volumes \
  --set tolerations[0].effect=NoSchedule,tolerations[0].key=node-
role.kubernetes.io/master
```

```
NAME: nfs-provisioner
LAST DEPLOYED: Fri Jan 24 12:42:24 2020
NAMESPACE: kube-system
STATUS: deployed
REVISION: 1
TEST SUITE: None
```

7.6.4 nginx-ingress

Create the yaml file:

```
]$ cat ingress.yaml
controller:
  tolerations:
  - effect: NoSchedule
    key: node-role.kubernetes.io/master
  service:
    type: NodePort
  externalIPs:
  - (static IP of the master node)
  config:
    proxy-body-size: '0'
    ssl-protocols: 'TLSv1 TLSv1.1 TLSv1.2'
```



```
ssl-ciphers: 'ECDHE-ECDSA-CHACHA20-POLY1305:ECDHE-RSA-CHACHA20-
POLY1305:ECDHE-ECDSA-AES128-GCM-SHA256:ECDHE-RSA-AES128-GCM-
SHA256:ECDHE-ECDSA-AES256-GCM-SHA384:E[.]'
defaultBackend:
tolerations:
- effect: NoSchedule
key: node-role.kubernetes.io/master
```

Install nginx-ingress in the K8s master node:

```
]$ sudo helm install -name cluster-ingress --namespace kube-system -f ingress.yaml
stable/nginx-ingress
NAME: cluster-ingress
LAST DEPLOYED: Fri Jan 24 12:47:28 2020
NAMESPACE: kube-system
STATUS: deployed
REVISION: 1
TEST SUITE: None
NOTES:
The nginx-ingress controller has been installed.
```

Get the application URL by running these commands:

```
export HTTP_NODE_PORT=$(kubectl --namespace kube-system get services -o
jsonpath="{.spec.ports[0].nodePort}" cluster-ingress-nginx-ingress-controller)
export HTTPS_NODE_PORT=$(kubectl --namespace kube-system get services -o
jsonpath="{.spec.ports[1].nodePort}" cluster-ingress-nginx-ingress-controller)
export NODE_IP=$(kubectl --namespace kube-system get nodes -o
jsonpath="{.items[0].status.addresses[1].address}")
```

```
echo "Visit http://$NODE_IP:$HTTP_NODE_PORT to access your application via HTTP."
echo "Visit https://$NODE_IP:$HTTPS_NODE_PORT to access your application via HTTPS."
```

An example Ingress that makes use of the controller:

```
apiVersion: extensions/v1beta1
kind: Ingress
metadata:
  annotations:
    kubernetes.io/ingress.class: nginx
  name: example
  namespace: foo
spec:
  rules:
  - host: www.example.com
    http:
      paths:
      - backend:
          serviceName: exampleService
          servicePort: 80
```



```
path: /
# This section is only required if TLS is to be enabled for the Ingress
tls:
  - hosts:
    - www.example.com
    secretName: example-tls
```

If TLS is enabled for the Ingress, a Secret containing the certificate and key must also be provided:

```
apiVersion: v1
kind: Secret
metadata:
  name: example-tls
  namespace: foo
data:
  tls.crt: <base64 encoded cert>
  tls.key: <base64 encoded key>
type: kubernetes.io/tls
```

7.6.5 Install the cert-manager certificate

Update the K8s front-node hostname. You can register a new entry for the front-node in a DNS, or use the [Dynamic DNS service](#) for the EGI FedCloud infrastructure.

For this particular scenario, the Dynamic DNS service of EGI was used. To update the hostname of the master, after you have obtained the host secret from the service, just run the command:

```
]$ curl https://notebooks-panosc.fedcloud-
tf.fedcloud.eu:X97JBX27S7@nsupdate.fedcloud.eu/nic/update
Create the cert-manager namespace:
```

```
]$ sudo kubectl create namespace cert-manager
namespace/cert-manager created
```

```
]$ sudo kubectl apply --validate=false -f https://raw.githubusercontent.com/jetstack/cert-
manager/release-0.12/deploy/manifests/00-crds.yaml
[.]
```

```
]$ sudo helm repo add jetstack https://charts.jetstack.io
"jetstack" has been added to your repositories
```

```
]$ sudo helm repo update
Hang tight while we grab the latest from your chart repositories...
...Successfully got an update from the "jetstack" chart repository
...Successfully got an update from the "stable" chart repository
Update Complete. ✨ Happy Helming!✨
```

```
]$ cat certmanager.yaml
webhook:
```



```
enabled: false
ingressShim:
  defaultIssuerName: letsencrypt-prod
  defaultIssuerKind: ClusterIssuer
tolerations:
- effect: NoSchedule
  key: node-role.kubernetes.io/master
cainjector.tolerations:
- effect: NoSchedule
  key: node-role.kubernetes.io/master
```

Install the cert-manager in the K8s master node:

```
]$ sudo helm install --name certs-man \
  --namespace cert-manager --version=0.12.0 \
  -f certmanager.yaml jetstack/cert-manager
NAME: certs-man
LAST DEPLOYED: Fri Jan 24 13:09:32 2020
NAMESPACE: cert-manager
STATUS: deployed
REVISION: 1
TEST SUITE: None
NOTES:
cert-manager has been deployed successfully!
[.]
```

7.6.6 ClusterIssuer

Create the ClusterIssuer in the K8s master node:

```
]$ cat clusterissuer.yaml
apiVersion: cert-manager.io/v1alpha2
kind: ClusterIssuer
metadata:
  name: letsencrypt-prod
spec:
  acme:
    email: giuseppe.larocca@egi.eu
    server: https://acme-v02.api.letsencrypt.org/directory
    privateKeySecretRef:
      name: cluster-issuer-account-key
    # Add a single challenge solver, HTTP01 using nginx
    solvers:
    - http01:
      ingress:
        class: nginx
```

Install the ClusterIssuer in the K8s master node

```
]$ sudo kubectl apply -f clusterissuer.yaml
```

clusterissuer.cert-manager.io/letsencrypt-prod created

7.6.7 JupyterHub

Create the jupyter configuration file for PaNOSC in the K8s master node:

proxy:

```
# FIXME NEEDS INPUT
secretToken: "XXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXX"
service:
  #type: 8888
  type: NodePort
```

ingress:

```
enabled: true
annotations:
  kubernetes.io/tls-acme: "true"
hosts:
  # FIXME NEEDS INPUT
  - notebooks-panosc.fedcloud-tf.fedcloud.eu
tls:
  - hosts:
    # FIXME NEEDS INPUT
    - notebooks-panosc.fedcloud-tf.fedcloud.eu
  secretName: acme-tls-catchall
```

singleuser:

```
storage:
  capacity: 10Gi
  dynamic:
    storageAccessModes: ["ReadWriteMany"]
memory:
  limit: 1G
  guarantee: 128M
cpu:
  limit: 1
  guarantee: .02
image:
  name: eginotebooks/single-user
  tag: "2044ab8"
```

hub:

```
image:
  name: enolfc/hub
  tag: "20200316.02"
extraEnv:
  JUPYTER_ENABLE_LAB: 1
  OAUTH2_AUTHORIZE_URL: https://proxy.umbrellaid.org/saml2sp/OIDC/authorization
  OAUTH2_TOKEN_URL: https://proxy.umbrellaid.org/OIDC/token
  OAUTH_CALLBACK_URL: https://notebooks-panosc.fedcloud-
```

tf.fedcloud.eu/hub/oauth_callback

extraConfig:

```

volume-handling: |-
  from egi_hub_addons.spawner import datahub_pod_modifier
  c.KubeSpawner.modify_pod_hook = datahub_pod_modifier(onezone_url='https://onezone-
panosc.egi.eu',                                oneprovider_host='oneprovider-pn.onezone-
panosc.egi.eu',
force_proxy_io=True,                            force_direct_io=False)
  c.JupyterHub.authenticate_prometheus = False
  c.JupyterHub.log_level = 'DEBUG'
  c.JupyterHub.template_paths = ['/usr/local/share/egi-hub/templates/']

```

auth:

state:

enabled: true

FIXME NEEDS INPUT

cryptoKey: "XX"

type: custom

admin:

access: true

users:

- XXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXX

custom:

className: egiauthenticator.oidc.OIDCAuthenticator

config:

client_id: "XXX-XXXXXXXX-XXXX-XXXX-XXXX-XXXXXXXXXXXX"

client_secret: "XX"

oauth_callback_url: "https://notebooks-panosc.fedcloud-tf.fedcloud.eu/hub/oauth_callback"

token_url: "https://proxy.umbrellaid.org/OIDC/token"

userdata_url: "https://proxy.umbrellaid.org/OIDC/userinfo"

scope: ["openid", "profile", "email"]

client_auth_method: "client_secret_post"

username_key: "name"

onezone_url: "https://onezone-panosc.egi.eu"

onezone_idp: "UmbrellaID"

oneprovider_host: "cesnet-pn.onezone-panosc.egi.eu"

]\$ sudo helm repo update

Hang tight while we grab the latest from your chart repositories...

...Successfully got an update from the "jetstack" chart repository

...Successfully got an update from the "jupyterhub" chart repository

...Successfully got an update from the "stable" chart repository

Update Complete. ✨ Happy Helming! ✨

Create the namespace:

]\$ sudo kubectl create namespace panosc

namespace/panosc created

Install the Jupyterhub in the namespace:


```
]$ sudo helm install panosc --namespace panosc --version 0.9.0-beta.2 -f panosc.yaml  
jupyterhub/jupyterhub
```


7.7 PART V - Configure a Binder instance to spawn Jupyter notebooks

7.7.1 Registry

Create the registry.yaml configuration file for helm:

```
]$ cat registry.yaml
persistence:
  enabled: false

secrets:
  httpswd: "binder:$2y$05$1Gc[..]AsSILbNVak11s4VtK"

ingress:
  enabled: true
  annotations:
    kubernetes.io/tls-acme: "true"
    ingress.kubernetes.io/proxy-body-size: "0"
  hosts: [registry-panosc.ops.fedcloud.eu]
  tls:
    - hosts: [registry-panosc.ops.fedcloud.eu]
      secretName: acme-tls-registry
```

Create the namespace:

```
]$ sudo kubectl create namespace registry
namespace/registry created
```

Install the registry in the namespace:

```
]$ sudo helm install registry stable/docker-registry \
  -f registry.yaml --namespace registry
[.]
```

7.7.2 Binder

Create the binder.yaml configuration file for helm:

```
]$ cat binder.yaml
---
config:
  BinderHub:
    auth_enabled: true
    hub_url: https://binder-panosc.fedcloud-tf.fedcloud.eu/hub
    use_registry: true
    image_prefix: registry-panosc.ops.fedcloud.eu/binder-
    build_image: jupyter/repo2docker:0.10.0
```

use_named_servers: true

registry:

url: "https://registry-panosc.ops.fedcloud.eu"

username: binder

password: *****

dind:

enabled: true

daemonset:

extraArgs:

- --mtu=1392

ingress:

enabled: true

annotations:

kubernetes.io/tls-acme: "true"

hosts: [binder-panosc.fedcloud-tf.fedcloud.eu]

tls:

- hosts:

- binder-panosc.fedcloud-tf.fedcloud.eu

secretName: acme-tls-binder

service:

type: NodePort

jupyterhub:

proxy:

secretToken: "*****"

service:

type: NodePort

ingress:

enabled: true

annotations:

kubernetes.io/tls-acme: "true"

hosts: [binder-panosc.fedcloud-tf.fedcloud.eu]

tls:

- hosts: [binder-panosc.fedcloud-tf.fedcloud.eu]

secretName: acme-tls-binder

singleuser:

storage:

type: none

capacity: 1Gi

dynamic:

storageAccessModes: ["ReadWriteMany"]

memory:

limit: 3.5G

```
guarantee: 1G
cpu:
  limit: 2
  guarantee: .02
cmd: jupyterhub-singleuser
imagePullSecret:
  enabled: true
  registry: registry-panosc.ops.fedcloud.eu
  username: binder
  password: *****

hub:
  baseUrl: "/hub"
  allowNamedServers: true
  namedServerLimitPerUser: 0
  image:
    name: enolfc/hub
    tag: "20200316.02"
  extraConfig:
    volume-handling: |
      c.JupyterHub.authenticate_prometheus = False
      c.JupyterHub.log_level = 'DEBUG'
      c.JupyterHub.template_paths = ['/usr/local/share/egi-hub/templates/']
  extraEnv:
    OAUTH2_AUTHORIZE_URL: https://proxy.umbrellaid.org/saml2sp/OIDC/authorization
    OAUTH2_TOKEN_URL: https://proxy.umbrellaid.org/OIDC/token
  services:
    binder:
      admin: true
      oauth_redirect_uri: "http://binder-panosc.fedcloud-tf.fedcloud.eu/oauth_callback"
      oauth_client_id: "binder-egi"
      apiToken: "XXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXX"

auth:
  type: custom
  state:
    enabled: true
    cryptoKey: "XXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXX"
  admin:
    access: true
    users:
      - efernandez
      - efernandez2
      - glarocca5
  custom:
    className: egiauthenticator.oidc.OIDCAuthenticator
    config:
      client_id: "XXX-XXXXXXXX-XXXX-XXXX-XXXX-XXXXXXXXXXXX"
      client_secret: "*****"
```



```
oauth_callback_url: "https://binder-panosc.fedcloud-tf.fedcloud.eu/hub/oauth_callback"  
token_url: "https://proxy.umbrellaid.org/OIDC/token"  
userdata_url: "https://proxy.umbrellaid.org/OIDC/userinfo"  
scope: ["openid", "profile", "email"]  
client_auth_method: "client_secret_post"  
username_key: "name"  
onezone_url: "https://onezone-panosc.egi.eu"  
onezone_idp: "eduTEAMS"  
oneprovider_host: "cesnet-op.onezone-panosc.egi.eu"
```

```
cull:  
  timeout: 900  
  every: 300
```

```
]$ sudo helm install binder jupyterhub/binderhub \  
  --version=0.2.0-n153.h7db895c \  
  --namespace=binder -f binder.yaml
```

